

Comparison of Grouped and Explicit Precursor Treatments for Delayed Neutron Production

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ABSTRACT

Delayed neutrons are conventionally represented with group-wise parameters, where each fissionable isotope is characterized by a total delayed neutron yield distributed among a small number of pseudo-precursors with corresponding relative abundances and decay constants. These parameters originate from exponential fits to experimentally measured decay curves and from summation analyses of fission product data performed decades ago. The availability of more comprehensive nuclear data now enables explicit modeling of delayed neutron precursors directly through the Bateman equation system. Building on the extended point kinetics solver developed at PSI, which explicitly models each delayed neutron precursor rather than using grouped parameters, this work calculates the physical delayed neutron fraction and compares it with that obtained from the conventional grouped formulation. The comparison, performed for six critical configurations from the ICSBEP handbook, revealed discrepancies between the results of the two approaches. An uncertainty analysis of the explicitly calculated delayed neutron fraction, conducted for the Stacy-30 assembly using perturbed fission yield and decay data, showed that these uncertainties do not account for the observed differences. Finally, the transient response of the extended point kinetics solver was analyzed to assess its sensitivity to nuclear data uncertainties. The initial results indicate systematic differences between the two formulations, which may motivate further work toward improving the alignment between the grouped delayed neutron parameters and the underlying fission yield and decay data.

Keywords: delayed neutrons, explicit precursor modeling, extended point kinetics

1. INTRODUCTION

Although constituting just a tiny fraction of all neutrons emitted in fission (<1%), delayed neutrons play a crucial role in the controllability of a nuclear system. They are emitted during the de-excitation of daughters of highly unstable fission products undergoing β^- decay. As de-excitation can be considered nearly instantaneous compared to the preceding β^- decay, the term delayed neutron precursor is attributed to the fission product undergoing β^- decay.

In the mid-20th century, the study of individual delayed neutron precursors could not be performed directly due to limitations in isotope-separation technology. Consequently, precursor nuclides were grouped into a small number of *pseudo-precursors*, each characterized by an effective half-life, yield, and energy spectrum. This approach was first established by Keepin and co-workers [1] at Los Alamos in the 1950s through pulse and steady-state irradiations of fissile isotopes, from which the six-group yields and half-lives were derived and shown to provide accurate fits to experimental decay curves. Later, in the 1980s, summation-based evaluations such as those by Brady and England [2],[3] incorporated the fission-yield and decay data available at the time, allowing group parameters to be derived from explicit precursor information using codes like CINDER [4]. However, the delayed neutron data in the current

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evaluated libraries still rely on these historical evaluations, with the ENDF/B [5] retaining the six-group formulation, while the JEFF [6] library adopted an eight-group structure with standardized half-lives to improve consistency across isotopes [4]. At the same time, more comprehensive nuclear data now allow simulating the explicit precursor inventory directly through the solution of the Bateman equations [7].

The main motivation for the present analysis stems from the ongoing development of an extended point kinetics solver that explicitly models each delayed neutron precursor rather than using grouped parameters [7], [8]. Originally developed for molten salt reactor studies to investigate the effects of fuel circulation and online reprocessing on delayed neutron behavior and reactor kinetics, this solver also provides a framework for assessing the consistency between explicit and grouped treatments, as well as for potentially deriving new group parameters.

The present work focuses on one aspect of this development, namely the application of the explicit precursor treatment to the calculation of the physical delayed neutron fraction. The analysis compares the values obtained in this way with those derived from the conventional group-wise representation. The comparison is performed for six critical experiments from the ICSBEP handbook [9].

The differences observed between the results of the two methods for some of the examined cases motivated the uncertainty analysis of the explicitly calculated delayed neutron fraction, here denoted as β_0^* , with respect to nuclear data uncertainties. The uncertainty analysis was performed for β_0^* by propagating the fission-yield and decay-data uncertainties on one of the cases (Stacy-30). The results showed that the difference between the two methods remains significant considering the calculated uncertainties.

Finally, the sensitivity of the kinetic response of the extended point kinetics solver to data uncertainties was assessed through a reactivity-insertion transient for the Stacy-30 case. The responses of the perturbed cases were then presented alongside those obtained using the grouped effective parameters generated by the transport code.

Transport simulations were performed with the Serpent 2.2 Monte Carlo code [10] using the JEFF-3.1.1 [11] and ENDF/B-VII.0 [12] nuclear data libraries. From these calculations, the group-wise delayed neutron parameters and the corresponding burnup and decay matrices were obtained. The latter served as inputs to an external MATLAB routine, which forms part of the extended point kinetics solver framework and is used for the delayed neutron fraction evaluation. The transient simulations presented in the final part of this work were subsequently performed with the extended point kinetics solver.

2. COMPARISON OF THE DELAYED NEUTRON FRACTION FROM GROUPED AND EXPLICIT PRECURSOR DATA

To assess the consistency between the results of the two approaches for calculating the delayed neutron production, six critical assemblies from the ICSBEP database were analyzed (listed in Table I). These benchmark cases were selected because the iterated fission probability (IFP) method implemented in Serpent has been validated for calculating effective point kinetics parameters on these systems [13], and therefore the physical delayed neutron fraction obtained using the grouped formulation can also be assumed to serve as a reliable reference for this comparison.

The first delayed neutron fraction, representing the value calculated with the grouped approach, is provided by the Serpent analog estimator. It corresponds to a Monte Carlo evaluation of the following:

$$\beta_0^{Serpent} \cong \frac{\int_V \int_0^\infty \sum_k \frac{\bar{\nu}_{d,k}}{\bar{\nu}_{p,k}(E) + \bar{\nu}_{d,k}} F_k(\vec{r}, E) d^3r dE}{\int_V \int_0^\infty F(\vec{r}, E) d^3r dE}, \quad (1)$$

where $\bar{\nu}_{p,k}(E)$ is the mean prompt neutron yield for the fissionable isotope k , which depends on energy, while the mean delayed neutron yield $\bar{\nu}_{d,k}$ is nearly constant up to about 5 MeV and its energy

dependence is therefore neglected [14]. The term $F_k(\vec{r}, E)$ represents the fission rate density of isotope k , and $F(\vec{r}, E)$ the total fission rate per unit energy and volume.

The second delayed neutron fraction, obtained through the explicit treatment of individual delayed neutron precursors, is calculated as the ratio between the total delayed neutron production rate from all precursors and the total neutron production rate. It is expressed as:

$$\beta_0^* = \frac{1}{\bar{\nu}F} \sum_k P_{n,k} \lambda_k N_{k,eq}, \quad (2)$$

where $P_{n,k}$ is the delayed neutron emission probability of precursor k , λ_k its decay constant, and $N_{k,eq}$ the equilibrium concentration of the precursor under steady-state conditions. The term $\bar{\nu}$ denotes the average total neutron yield per fission, and F the total fission rate.

To obtain the equilibrium precursor concentrations $N_{k,eq}$, the burnup matrix generated by Serpent was extracted and used in an external MATLAB burnup routine to evolve the initial nuclide vector for one hour. The external burnup procedure used the CRAM solver in the 32nd-order IPF approximation form [8], [15]. The extracted burnup matrices corresponded to simulations performed at 50 W power. The $P_{n,k} \lambda_k$ terms from Equation (2) are contained in the decay matrix, which was obtained separately from zero-power Serpent simulations.

The total fission rate F from Equation (2) was estimated from the same set of matrices by removing the decay terms from the full burnup matrix and applying the resulting matrix to the actinide vector to compute all actinide reaction rates. Summation of this reaction rate vector cancels out the transmutation terms, leaving only the total fission rate.

For the average total neutron yield $\bar{\nu}$ in Equation (2), the value reported by Serpent was adopted. Although it includes the delayed neutron component derived from the grouped formulation, this approximation is considered sufficient because the objective of the analysis is to assess the consistency of delayed neutron production rates between the two approaches. Expressing the results in terms of the delayed neutron fraction is equivalent to applying the same scaling factor, $1/(\bar{\nu}F)$, to the delayed neutron production rate in both cases. However, comparing β_0 in pcm units provides a clearer and more intuitive basis for interpretation than comparing absolute production rates.

In Table II, the explicitly calculated delayed neutron fractions β_0^* , the values obtained with the grouped formulation β_0^{Serpent} , and their respective differences are reported. The table also includes the effective delayed neutron fractions obtained using Meulekamp's method [16], along with the corresponding experimental values [13], to support the validity of the simulations. Since the experimental β_{eff} for the Stacy-30 was not available, the MCNP5 result reported in [13] is shown instead, noting that Serpent has been validated for this configuration based on Rossi-alpha measurements. All values are reported with statistical uncertainties corresponding to one standard deviation.

Table I. Description of analyzed benchmarks

Case	Description
Godiva	A bare sphere of highly enriched (94 wt% U-235) uranium
Jezebel	A bare sphere of plutonium (95 at% Pu-239)
Skidoo	A bare sphere of uranium (98 at% U-233)
Popsy	A plutonium (94 wt% Pu-239) sphere surrounded by a thick reflector of natural uranium
Flattop 23	A uranium (98 at% U-233) sphere surrounded by a thick reflector of natural uranium
Stacy-30	Unreflected cylindrical tank with uranyl nitrate solution (~10 wt% U-235)

Table II. Physical delayed neutron fractions calculated from the precursor inventory (β_0^*) and by the Serpent analog estimator ($\beta_0^{Serpent}$), together with effective delayed neutron fractions obtained from Serpent and experiments. All values are expressed in units of pcm.

Case	Library	β_0^*	$\beta_0^{Serpent}$	Diff.	$\beta_{eff}^{Serpent}$	$\beta_{eff}^{Experimental}$
Godiva	ENDF/B-VII.0	690	644 ± 1	46	675 ± 1	659 ± 10
	JEFF-3.1.1	620	639 ± 1	-19	674 ± 1	
Jezebel	ENDF/B-VII.0	210	205 ± 1	5	197 ± 1	194 ± 10
	JEFF-3.1.1	215	208 ± 1	7	202 ± 1	
Skidoo	ENDF/B-VII.0	265	281 ± 1	-15	310 ± 1	290 ± 10
	JEFF-3.1.1	362	278 ± 1	83	309 ± 1	
Popsy	ENDF/B-VII.0	513	538 ± 1	-25	270 ± 1	276 ± 7
	JEFF-3.1.1	487	557 ± 1	-70	281 ± 1	
Flattop 23	ENDF/B-VII.0	540	580 ± 1	-40	358 ± 1	360 ± 9
	JEFF-3.1.1	581	589 ± 1	-8	366 ± 1	
Stacy-30	ENDF/B-VII.0	787	660 ± 1	127	738 ± 1	*763 ± 4 (MCNP5 result)
	JEFF-3.1.1	610	673 ± 1	-63	754 ± 1	

The comparison shows a good agreement between the explicit and grouped approaches for the Pu-239 fast system (Jezebel) and a relatively good agreement for the U-235 fast system (Godiva), indicating that the fission yields for these isotopes, in combination with the decay data, are consistent with the grouped parameters in both ENDF/B-VII.0 and JEFF-3.1.1. For the bare U-233 system (Skidoo), the results are in fair agreement in ENDF/B-VII.0 but show a notable deviation in JEFF-3.1.1 (about 30% overestimation relative to the grouped value), indicating inconsistencies between the explicit and grouped data for U-233 in the fast spectrum. For the reflected Pu-239 system (Popsy), the results show a moderate difference in ENDF/B-VII.0 and a larger deviation in JEFF-3.1.1. This may indicate mismatches in the U-238 fast-spectrum data in the reflector region, which accounts for approximately 24% of total fissions in the system. For the reflected U-233 system (Flattop-23), the results show general consistency for both libraries. However, in JEFF-3.1.1 it was already observed in Skidoo that the U-233 explicit data tend to overestimate the delayed neutron fraction, while the explicit data for U-238, as indicated by the Popsy results, appear to lead to an underestimation. Since in Flattop-23 approximately 74% of fissions occur on U-233 and about 20% on U-238, this combination may lead to a compensation between the two effects, resulting in an apparent agreement between the explicit and grouped data. For the thermal U-235 system (Stacy-30), the results indicate discrepancies in both libraries, which are more pronounced in ENDF/B-VII.0. Since more than 99.5% of fissions occur on U-235 and less than 0.5% on U-238, the deviation can be attributed to differences in the thermal U-235 fission yields together with the decay data, which do not appear to be fully consistent with the grouped parameters.

3. PROPAGATION OF UNCERTAINTIES IN THE EXPLICITLY CALCULATED DELAYED NEUTRON FRACTION

The discrepancies observed between the delayed neutron fractions obtained from the grouped and explicit approaches motivated an uncertainty analysis to examine the dependence of the explicitly calculated β_0^* on nuclear data uncertainties.

To identify which nuclear data the explicitly calculated delayed neutron fraction depends on, the expression in Equation (2) can be expanded as:

$$\beta_0^* = \frac{1}{\nu} \sum_k P_{n_k} \sum_j x_j Y_{kj}, \quad (3)$$

where x_j is the fraction of total fissions occurring on isotope j , and $Y_{k,j}$ is the cumulative fission yield of precursor k originating from isotope j . The cumulative fission yields determine the equilibrium concentrations of the precursors and, in turn, depend on the independent fission yields and decay data, including decay constants and branching ratios. The information on the independent fission yields and decay data is contained in the burnup matrix generated by Serpent, which is used in the previously described one-hour evolution of the initial nuclide vector to obtain the equilibrium precursor concentrations. Accordingly, in this analysis it was sufficient to propagate the uncertainties of the independent fission yields and decay data through the solution into the explicitly calculated delayed neutron fraction. Regarding the decay data, only the decay constants were perturbed, while the uncertainty propagation of branching ratios was not considered.

The JEFF-3.1.1 library and the Stacy-30 thermal assembly were selected for this study. This choice was motivated by the availability of perturbed fission yield samples for U-235 (thermal) and U-238 (0.4 MeV and 14 MeV), which were generated with the GEF code (version 2019) based on JEFF-3.1.1 data and distributed within the TENDL-2021 database [17]. The decay data were perturbed independently by sampling precursor half-lives from Gaussian distributions using the standard deviations provided in the evaluated datasets. For the Stacy-30 case, the explicit formulation included 157 delayed neutron precursors from the JEFF-3.1.1 library. Results obtained with the JEFF-3.3 and JEFF-4.0 fission yield and decay data are also additionally included for comparison.

Figure 1 shows the physical delayed neutron fractions obtained using JEFF-3.1.1, JEFF-3.3, JEFF-4.0, and the 100 perturbed-library cases. No direct perturbation was applied to the total delayed neutron yield or to the group abundances in the simulations. However, an uncertainty of $\pm 3\%$ was associated to the grouped delayed neutron fraction, following the recommendation from [5], which reports that the standard deviation of approximately $\pm 3\%$ can be expected for the effective delayed neutron fraction calculated using the recommended total delayed neutron yield of 0.0162 for thermal fission of U-235, which is used in the JEFF library.

The delayed neutron fraction obtained with the explicit approach exhibits, as expected, sensitivity to perturbations in the fission yield and decay data. Nevertheless, the propagated uncertainty remains too small to account for the observed difference between the explicit and grouped approaches. These results also provide an insight into the magnitude of nuclear data uncertainties in the explicitly calculated delayed neutron fraction. Figure 2 presents the delayed neutron fractions corresponding to the 30 most important precursors. Although the three JEFF libraries yield comparable total delayed neutron fractions, variations are observed on individual precursor level, with JEFF 3.1.1 generally differing the most from the two newer evaluations.

Figure 1. Delayed neutron fraction of the Stacy-30 configuration calculated by the two different approaches: explicit (from the full nuclide vector, red points), and grouped (calculated by Serpent using group parameters, blue points)

Figure 2. Delayed neutron fractions of the 30 most important precursors, which, when averaged over all simulated cases, account for 96.5% of the total delayed neutron production.

4. SENSITIVITY OF THE EXTENDED POINT KINETICS SOLVER TO NUCLEAR DATA UNCERTAINTIES

The response of the previously mentioned extended point kinetics solver was tested for its sensitivity to nuclear data uncertainties. The equilibrium precursor concentrations prior to the transient were obtained following the same procedure described in the previous section for calculating the physical delayed neutron fraction with the explicit approach.

For the kinetics simulations presented, an approximation was adopted in which all delayed neutrons were assumed to have equal effectiveness, such that the total effective delayed neutron fraction corresponds to the value obtained using the Meulekamp's method [16]. In this way, all simulations correspond to the same total effective delayed neutron fraction, while only the distribution among precursors with different half-lives varies.

The analyzed case corresponds to a temporal response to a 0.5 \$ reactivity insertion in the Stacy-30 assembly, presented in Figure 3. The responses of the nominal and 100 perturbed cases are shown as gray lines, with the two bounding cases shown in red (fastest) and green (slowest). The response of the conventional eight-group point kinetics model is represented by the black line positioned between the two bounding cases. The fastest response reaches the point where the neutron population increases by a factor of 100 at 16.77 s, the slowest at 21.45 s, and the grouped eight-group model at 20.65 s, while the nominal-library explicit case nearly coincides with the slowest response.

In the right part of the Figure 3, the relative contributions of individual precursors to the total delayed neutron fraction are shown in the form of a cumulative distribution function (CDF) as a function of their half-lives. This graph also includes the distributions of the grouped precursors for both the effective and physical delayed neutron fractions. They almost perfectly overlap, indicating that the effectivity of each group is nearly identical. This is expected, since the spectra of the grouped pseudo-precursors are superpositions of many individual precursor spectra contributing to the same group, which results in homogenized spectral characteristics and, consequently, similar effectiveness among the groups. For individual precursors, however, the assumption of equal effectiveness remains uncertain, as their delayed neutron spectra can differ significantly.

Figure 3. Left: Neutron population response following a 0.5 \$ reactivity insertion. Gray dashed lines represent the nominal case and 100 cases with perturbed fission yield and decay data, while the two extreme cases are highlighted in color. The 8-group point kinetics reference solution is shown in black. Right: Cumulative distribution of the relative delayed neutron production fraction as a function of precursor half-life. The 8-group effective delayed neutron data are plotted as a black dashed line, while the physical delayed neutron data are shown as a blue dotted line.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This study used the explicit precursor treatment implemented within the framework of the extended point kinetics solver [8] to calculate the physical delayed neutron fraction and to propagate nuclear data uncertainties to its response to a reactivity insertion transient.

The comparison between the delayed neutron fraction values obtained using the explicit precursor treatment and those derived from the conventional grouped representation was performed for six ICSBEP configurations. The results showed good consistency for fast systems dominated by Pu-239 and U-235 fissions, while larger deviations were observed for U-233, U-238 fast systems and for thermal U-235 system. These deviations suggest that, for the corresponding isotopes and spectra, inconsistencies exist between the grouped delayed neutron parameters and the underlying fission yield and decay datasets used in evaluated libraries.

Uncertainty analysis for a single case (Stacy-30), using perturbed fission yield and decay data, revealed that these uncertainties could not explain for the observed bias between the two approaches. In future work, the uncertainty propagation will be extended to all benchmark cases, and the uncertainties associated with the grouped delayed neutron parameters will also be considered where applicable.

Finally, the sensitivity of the extended point kinetics solver's response to nuclear data uncertainties was examined through a reactivity-insertion transient, where the spread among responses was analyzed with respect to the contributions of precursors with different half lives.

Initial findings suggest that the grouped delayed neutron parameters are not fully consistent with the underlying fission yield and decay data. The precursor-wise formulation presented here provides a basis for future work aimed at extending point kinetics models to include explicit precursor treatment where of interest.

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